

Optical addressability of the aryl nitrene spin triplet

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Abstract

Optically addressable spin systems are key to quantum technologies, but solid-state defects like NV⁻ centers face challenges in scalability and tunability. Here, we computationally explore aryl nitrenes as molecular alternatives. High-accuracy calculations confirm a robust triplet ground state with spin-selective intersystem crossing and spin-vibronic-mediated reverse intersystem crossing, enabling efficient spin-state initialization. While pristine aryl nitrene has weak optical transitions, targeted chemical modifications significantly enhance its emission capabilities without disrupting the symmetry rules governing the spin-state preparation mechanism. Combined with recent advances in nitrene stabilization and positioning, these results establish aryl nitrenes as promising candidates for molecular spin qubits.

The ability to control nuclear or electron spins via spectroscopy is essential for developing devices for quantum sensing,¹ quantum networks or quantum information.² In general, a quantum sensor requires a system with discrete energy levels, which is prone to be easily initialized, read-out and manipulated through spectroscopic means. Analogously, in a quantum network, such systems are essential to enable the information to be transferred between the static qubit, that stores and processes the information, and the flying qubits, which transmit the information. Since the static qubits operate in the microwave range while flying qubits are in the optical domain, quantum interfaces are needed for efficient information transfer. Optically addressable spin systems (OASSs) are promising candidates for this role,^{3,4} as their qubit states can be prepared and read out using spectroscopic techniques like optically detected magnetic resonance.⁵⁻⁷

For an efficient OASS, three key conditions need to be satisfied: (i) a ground state with spin multiplicity larger than one ($2S + 1 > 1$, with $S > 0$) to realize the spin initialization through a spin polarization process; (ii) a bright excited state for optical readout; (iii) a spin relaxation time (T_{rel}) larger than the optical lifetime (τ) to maintain spin polarization.

The nitrogen-vacancy (NV^-) center in diamond is a well-established and successful solid state OASS.^{8,9} Its spin-selective intersystem crossing (ISC) between the ^3E and ^1A excited states depopulates the $M_S = \pm 1$ triplet sublevels, while reverse ISC (RISC) repopulates the $M_S = 0$ triplet ground state, leading to efficient spin polarization. While NV^- centers exhibit exceptional coherence properties and have become a cornerstone in quantum sensing and spin-based technologies, challenges such as scalability,¹⁰ charge state stability,¹¹ and limited tunability,¹² hinder its integration into quantum platforms. Molecular systems offer a promising alternative, providing tunable electronic structures, ease of synthesis, and adaptable device integration.¹³⁻¹⁸ Metal complexes have been explored as molecular qubits,^{19,20} where spin initialization and readout occur via resonant excitation between a triplet ground state sublevel and a singlet excited state, enabled by zero-field splitting (ZFS).³ Likewise, fully organic radical-based materials have shown promising photophysical properties for molecular qubits, such as successful optical read-out through fluorescence-detected magnetic resonance spectroscopy and long spin coherence times.^{21,22} Diradicals with triplet ground states²³ are particularly appealing for NV^- -like spin initialization via selective (R)ISC pathways.^{24,25} A notable class of diradicals is “sextet” systems, where two unpaired electrons reside on the same atom in perpendicular atomic orbitals, leading to strong localization and large exchange interactions that favor a triplet ground state. Arylnitrenes fall into this category and have been extensively studied due to their high reactivity. Historically, they were characterized only in low-temperature matrices or single crystals as intermediates in arylazide photolysis.²⁶⁻²⁹ In these systems, nitrogen’s five valence electrons are distributed as follows: one electron forms a σ bond with the aryl fragment, another

remains as a lone pair, and the last two electrons occupy the p_x and p_y orbitals in a triplet configuration. Recently, Tan *et al.* synthesized and characterized a stable arylnitrene derivative using bulky substituents.³⁰ Its triplet ground state was confirmed via electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy and supported by wavefunction-based theoretical calculations. Additionally, Bardeen *et al.*³¹ generated nitrene species in crystalline arylazide samples through in-situ photolysis. The perfluorinated derivative displayed remarkable stability due to trapped N_2 molecules preventing oxygen-induced side reactions, while fluorine substituents protected the nitrene from thermal annealing during purification.

It follows that arylnitrene compounds can be a fruitful starting point to build NV^- center-like molecular qubits. To this end, in this work we explore the electronic structure of the pristine arylnitrene molecule and derivatives (Figure 1) to assess their suitability as an OASS. Specifically, we will focus on their ability to meet the key conditions (i and ii) described above for efficient spin initialization and readout processes. The article is organized as follows: First, we describe the electronic structure of the lowest triplet and singlet states. Next, we analyze the potential spin initialization mechanism within the Franck-Condon framework using symmetry arguments and high-accuracy calculations. In the fourth section, we examine the impact of spin-vibronic couplings on the RISC process. Finally, in section five, we explore chemical substitution as a strategy to design a bright arylnitrene derivative.

Figure 1. Molecular structures of the studied pristine arylnitrene (a) and its derivative (b).

The ground state triplet

Electronic structure calculations at both the DFT and NEVPT2 levels confirm that the ground state of the arylnitrene compound is a spin-triplet (X^3A_2 , where X denotes the ground electronic state), consistent with previous computational studies.^{26,27} The electronic configuration of the ground state triplet can be rationalized via the orbital interaction diagram between the aryl fragment and the three 2p electrons from the nitrogen atom. As depicted in Figure 2, symmetry-allowed interactions lift the

degeneracy of the nitrogen 2p orbitals: the $2p_z$ orbital is stabilized through a σ -bonding interaction with the singly occupied aryl $2\sigma_z$ orbital, while the $2p_x$ and $2p_y$ orbitals are destabilized, giving rise to the singly occupied n_x and n_y orbitals. Specifically, the highest singly occupied molecular orbital in aryl nitrene is n_x , which emerges from the interaction between the nitrogen $2p_x$ orbital and the aryl π -orbitals with b_1 symmetry. In contrast, n_y results from the interaction of the nitrogen $2p_y$ orbital with the highest occupied σ -orbital of the aryl fragment, which has b_2 symmetry. Notably, while the unpaired electron in n_y remains largely localized on the nitrogen atom, n_x exhibits significant delocalization onto the aryl π -system.

Figure 2. Orbital interaction diagram of aryl nitrene built from the aryl (right) and nitrogen (left) fragments. The aryl nitrene orbitals are shown starting from the first π orbital. For the fragments, only the orbitals with the largest contributions are shown. The C_{2v} symmetry labels are shown in parenthesis. The orbitals of both the fragments and the aryl nitrene (plots in the top-left rectangular frame) have been computed at PBE0/def2-TZVP level at the triplet ground state geometry. The symmetry labels are identified through green, blue, red and grey colors (a_1 , b_1 , b_2 and a_2 respectively). The positive phase of the orbitals has been colored following the same color code.

Many conventional organic diradicals hold an open-shell ground state singlet. High-spin multiplicity in the ground state is typically achieved by significantly decoupling the two unpaired electrons. However, even in those diradicals with a triplet ground state, the triplet-singlet energy gap is often small, making the low-spin state thermally accessible, an effect that can compromise optically detected magnetic resonance resolution.^{22,24,32} In contrast, the strong spatial confinement of the two unpaired electrons in aryl nitrenes ensures a robust triplet ground state with a substantial energy gap

relative to the open-shell singlet. This is supported by the strong exchange interaction between the n_x and n_y orbitals, quantified as $2K_{xy} = 0.714$ eV, and further corroborated by highly correlated calculations (Table 1), which place the open-shell singlet (1^1A_2) 0.857 eV above the triplet ground state (X^3A_2).

Low-lying electronic states

In addition to a stable triplet ground state, an effective molecular platform for optically addressable spins must exhibit a well-structured excited-state distribution capable of absorbing incident photons and utilizing this additional energy to drive the system toward the desired spin microstates. To accurately compute the low-lying electronic states, we employ multireference second-order perturbation theory calculations (see Methods section). The strongly correlated orbitals used to describe both triplet and singlet states are depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SA-CASSCF(10,10)/def2TZVP natural orbitals included in the (10,10) active space. The symmetry labels are defined within the C_{2v} point group, according to the cartesian reference shown on the left. The coloring follows the same color code defined in Figure 2.

FIC-NEVPT2(10,10) calculations at the triplet ground-state geometry (X^3A_2) of aryl nitrene are summarized in Table 1. Notably, the three lowest singlet excited states lie between the X^3A_2 and 1^3B_1 triplet states, closely resembling the energy scheme characteristic of NV^- centers.⁹ Furthermore, the predicted absolute and relative excited-state energies exhibit excellent agreement with previous ab initio calculations and spectroscopic measurements, further validating the reliability of our computational approach.^{26,33,34}

The lowest excited singlet states above the open-shell singlet (1^1A_2) are the totally symmetric 1^1A_1 and 2^1A_1 states (Table 1). These arise from a linear combination of the two closed-shell configurations, where both electrons occupy either the n_x or n_y orbitals. Specifically, the 1^1A_1 state has a greater contribution from the $(n_y)^2$ configuration, while the 2^1A_1 state is predominantly characterized by $(n_x)^2$ occupancy, leading to the larger energy of the latter than the former.

The first excited triplet state, 1^3B_1 , originates from the combination of two one-electron transition configurations: $3\pi \rightarrow n_x$ and $n_x \rightarrow 3\pi^*$, with the former contributing the most. Although the $X^3A_2 \rightarrow 1^3B_1$ transition is symmetry-allowed for one-photon absorption, its oscillator strength

remains notably low. This is primarily due to the dominant $3\pi \rightarrow n_x$ excitation exhibiting a strong intramolecular charge-transfer (intra-CT) character, which significantly reduces orbital overlap and weakens the transition intensity. In contrast, transitions to the higher 2^3A_2 and 2^3B_1 states exhibit significantly larger oscillator strengths, particularly for the latter, where the dominant $n_x \rightarrow 3\pi^*$ transition benefits from strong orbital overlap.

Table 1. Vertical excitation energies (in eV), main electronic configurations with the associated weights of the lowest singlet and triplet states of arylnitrene computed at FIC-NEVPT2(10,10)/def2TZVP level. Oscillator strengths in parentheses.

state	ΔE	main configurations	weight
X^3A_2	0.000	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(n_x)^1 $	0.81
1^1A_2	0.857	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(n_x)^1 $	0.77
1^1A_1	1.271	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^2 $	0.65
		$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_x)^2 $	0.11
2^1A_1	2.469	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_x)^2 $	0.61
		$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^2 $	0.14
1^3B_1	3.147 ($8 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^1(n_y)^1(n_x)^2 $	0.51
		$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(3\pi^*)^1 $	0.21
2^3A_2	3.425 (0.011)	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^1(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(n_x)^2 $	0.51
		$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(2\pi^*)^1 $	0.27
2^3B_1	4.269 (0.058)	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(3\pi^*)^1 $	0.39
		$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^1(n_y)^1(n_x)^2 $	0.28

Spin state initialization mechanism

Beyond ensuring proper triplet and singlet energetics, achieving efficient spin-state preparation through photoinduced relaxation requires spin-selective interstate transitions that facilitate the transformation between spin microstates, specifically, promoting the overpopulation of a particular triplet sublevel in the ground state. In organic molecules, such spin-state initialization mechanisms rely on spin-orbit coupling (SOC) properties. Therefore, to evaluate whether arylnitrene can undergo optically induced spin-state initialization, we analyze the SOC integrals between the low-lying triplet and singlet states.

The molecular symmetry of arylnitrene (C_{2v}) imposes strict selection rules on ISC (triplet-to-singlet) and RISC (singlet-to-triplet) processes. Following single-photon absorption into the low-lying excited triplet states, and assuming rapid internal conversion (IC) leading to population of the 1^3B_1 state, we evaluate the feasibility of ISC to the three lowest singlet states, 1^1A_2 , 1^1A_1 , and 2^1A_1 . In all cases, SOC is symmetry-allowed for transitions originating from the $M_S = \pm 1$ triplet sublevels

but forbidden from $M_S = 0$. This restriction arises because the spatial wavefunction of the 3B_1 state does not couple to 1A_1 or 1A_2 singlets via the L_z angular momentum operator (which transforms as A_2). However, coupling is allowed through L_x and L_y , which transform as B_1 and B_2 , respectively.

This symmetry-based selection is confirmed by the nonzero SOC values computed for ISC (Table 2). Notably, the largest spin-orbit interaction is observed for 2^1A_1 , with a magnitude similar or even larger than typical values found in organic chromophores undergoing ISC.³⁵⁻³⁷ Additionally, 2^1A_1 has the smallest energy gap with 1^3B_1 , further supporting the $1^3B_1 \rightarrow 2^1A_1$ transition as the most efficient ISC channel.

Table 2. SOC matrix elements (in cm^{-1}) and energy gaps between initial and final ($\Delta E = E_f - E_i$, in eV) triplet and singlet states potentially involved in ISC and RISC processes computed at CASSCF(10,10)/def2TZVP level at the triplet ground state geometry.

process	initial state	final state	SOC	ΔE
ISC	1^3B_1	1^1A_2	0.123	2.290
ISC	1^3B_1	1^1A_1	1.025	1.876
ISC	1^3B_1	2^1A_1	1.528	0.678
RISC	1^1A_2	X^3A_2	0.000	0.857
RISC	1^1A_1	X^3A_2	17.227	1.271
RISC	2^1A_1	X^3A_2	46.252	2.469

RISC pathways to the ground-state triplet are only allowed from the 1A_1 states (and not from 1A_2), as symmetry prohibits coupling between 3A_2 and 1A_2 states, in accordance with the El-Sayed's rules.^{38,39} Furthermore, both 1^1A_1 and 2^1A_1 can only couple to the $M_S = 0$ sublevel of the ground state, as A_1 spatial functions can only be transformed to A_2 symmetry via the L_z operator. Consequently, the spin transition is mediated by the S_z operator, enforcing $\Delta M_S = 0$.

Notably, the computed SOC values between the A_1 singlets and the ground-state triplet are more than an order of magnitude larger than those involved in the ISC pathways. This strong interaction can be rationalized by analyzing the dominant electronic configurations of the triplet and singlet states. In both RISC transitions, the primary mechanism involves a single-electron transfer between the n_x and n_y orbitals, corresponding predominantly to a transition between the nitrogen $2p_x$ and $2p_y$ orbitals. This process is highly efficient due to the direct orbital coupling via the L_z operator, which induces an orbital rotation about the z -axis.

Spin-vibronic reverse intersystem crossing

It is important to emphasize that, despite the strong coupling between the 1A_1 states and the ground-state triplet, RISC must compete with IC to the lowest singlet state, which is expected to be highly efficient due to spin conservation. As a result, the 1^1A_2 state is likely to act as an exciton

reservoir. One possible pathway for RISC could involve thermal activation via reverse IC from 1^1A_2 to 1^1A_1 . However, the energy gap between these singlet states (0.414 eV) significantly exceeds typical thermal energies, making this process unlikely under standard conditions. A potential strategy to enhance this mechanism would be to reduce the singlet-singlet energy gap through chemical substitution. Alternatively, spin-vibronic interactions could facilitate $1^1A_2 \rightarrow X^3A_2$ RISC by enabling mixing with higher-lying singlet states.

The previous analysis considered SOCs computed at the triplet ground-state geometry, following the Franck-Condon approximation. However, higher-order effects induced by vibrational motion, such as Herzberg-Teller (HT) effects and spin-vibronic coupling (SVC), can break symmetry and enhance state mixing, thereby facilitating the spin conversion process. As a result, the $1^1A_2 \rightarrow X^3A_2$ transition may proceed through a vibrationally assisted RISC pathway. The HT mechanism introduces corrections into the electronic wavefunction due to the nuclear motion, thus breaking the Franck-Condon approximation. The SVC mechanism arises from the 2nd order perturbation theory introducing the coupling between SOC and non-adiabatic couplings (NACs). Even though formally different, these two mechanisms can be quantitatively described by the following expression, which accounts for the influence of higher-lying excited states on SOCs through NACs, highlighting their role in enabling spin conversion beyond the Franck-Condon regime:⁴⁰⁻⁴²

$$V_{SV} \propto \sum_i \frac{\langle X^3A_2 | \hat{H}_{SOC} | \phi_i \rangle \langle \phi_i | \frac{\partial}{\partial Q_j} | 1^1A_2 \rangle}{E(\phi_i) - E(1^1A_2)} \quad (1)$$

in which, Q_j is the j -th vibrational normal mode, ϕ_i is the vibronic wavefunction of the higher-lying singlet excited state and $E(\phi_i)$ is the total energy (vibrational + electronic) of the electronic state. The term $\langle \phi_i | \partial/\partial Q_j | 1^1A_2 \rangle$ is the electronic NAC mixing the 1^1A_2 singlet with the higher-lying singlet excited states. By considering ϕ_i as the $1/2^1A_1$ singlet excited states, focusing on the sole electronic part of equation 1, we have that the NAC integrals $\langle 1/2^1A_1 | \partial/\partial Q_j | 1^1A_2 \rangle$ are nonzero by symmetry for a_2 normal modes.

To quantitatively evaluate the impact of vibrational motion, we displaced the molecular geometry by $\pm 0.1 \times Q_j$ (in which Q_j is the normal mode in cartesian coordinates) along the lowest-frequency a_2 normal mode (334 cm^{-1} ; see Figure S1), computed at the 1^1A_2 equilibrium geometry. Both geometry optimization and frequency calculations were performed at the SA-CASSCF(10,10)/def2-TZVP level. At the displaced geometries, we calculated the SOC matrix element for the $1^1A_2 \rightarrow X^3A_2$ transition, obtaining a consistent value of 0.889 cm^{-1} in both

displacement directions. Therefore, we infer that the a_2 mode effectively activates the coupling between the two states, facilitating spin conversion. Furthermore, because the SVC mechanism is mediated by A_1 states, the RISC process selectively populates the $M_S = 0$ sublevel of X^3A_2 , ensuring spin-state control during the transition.

Overall, these results are consistent with the following potential spin-state initialization mechanism in aryl nitrene: (i) initial photoabsorption to low-lying excited triplet states and fast IC to 1^3B_1 , (ii) ISC from $M_S = \pm 1$ triplet sublevels to the singlet manifold, predominantly to the 2^1A_1 state, and (iii) fast IC to the lowest excited singlet, 1^1A_2 , followed by spin-vibronic RISC to the $M_S = 0$ microstate of the X^3A_2 ground state (Figure 4). The recurrence of this cycle will result in an overpopulation of the $M_S = 0$ sublevels of the X^3A_2 ground state, representing a viable approach for spin initialization.

Figure 4. Energy diagram of the aryl nitrene compound within the vertical picture (triplet ground state geometry). The red and blue arrows define the absorption (ABS) and photoluminescence (PL) processes, respectively, in the triplet multiplicity. The thickness of the ABS arrows follows the magnitude of the oscillator strength of the excited states. The curved arrows define internal conversion (IC) processes. Grey arrows define the ISC and the Spin-Vibronic (SV) RISC.

Brightening triplet aryl nitrenes

The low oscillator strength of the 1^3B_1 state suggests a weak radiative $1^3B_1 \rightarrow X^3A_2$ transition, making it unfavorable against the ISC process and thereby enhancing the efficiency of spin-state initialization. However, for effective optical readout, a bright emissive state is essential, i.e., photoluminescence should not be completely quenched by ISC. This requirement can be addressed through strategic chemical modifications (*vide infra*). Similar approaches have been explored in systems designed for spin-photon interfaces and optically addressable qubits.¹⁶

Despite proving to bear the appropriate electronic structure for a potential state initialization process, the arylnitrene system suffers from a weak emission cross section accompanying the $1^3B_1 \leftrightarrow X^3A_2$ transition caused by its intra-CT character. Indeed, while the inclusion of vibronic effects, e.g., HT mechanism, can enhance the emission intensity, designing systems with an intrinsic high oscillator strength would be clearly desired. In this regard, the use of electron-donating and electron-withdrawing substituents can be an effective strategy to achieve this goal, locating them along the direction bearing the largest transition dipole moment component.⁴³ Nonetheless, the nature of the substituents and the anchoring sites must be carefully chosen to ensure retaining the electronic structure promoting the state initialization process. In this regard, it is worth considering that as long as the symmetry of the lowest triplet excited state remains the same (B_1), and as long as the singlet excited states active in the selective spin conversions energetically lie between the ground and first excited triplets, the overall state initialization mechanism persists. It follows that a strategy to gain emission cross section is through the stabilization of the 2^3B_1 state, which bears the largest oscillator strength thanks to its $\pi\pi^*$ nature (Table 1). This can be accomplished by either stabilizing or destabilizing the $3\pi^*$ and the n_x orbitals, respectively, which present atomic sites with a different electron density distribution (Figure 3), thus offering a selective modulation of their energy. For instance, the introduction of an amino group (electron-donating) in the *para* position would lead to the destabilization of the n_x orbital without perturbing the $3\pi^*$ one, since the latter bear a node in the electron density on that position. Simultaneously, the introduction of cyano groups (electron-withdrawing) on the two *meta* positions would lead to the stabilization of the $3\pi^*$ orbital, with a negligible effect on the energy of the n_x orbital. By combining these two chemical substitutions (Figure 1b), the energy associated with the $n_x \rightarrow 3\pi^*$ (3B_1) transition decreases, potentially becoming the lowest excited triplet state. In line with this prediction, Table 3 shows the vertical excitation energies computed at FIC-NEVPT2(10,10) level for this arylnitrene derivative, showing how the symmetry of the lowest triplet excited state is retained (3B_1), but with a change of its nature, which is now dominated by the $n_x \rightarrow 3\pi^*$ transition (see Figure S2 for the molecular orbitals). Consequently, the oscillator strength becomes two orders of magnitude larger than in the pristine arylnitrene (Table 1). The triplet state dominated by the $3\pi \rightarrow n_x$ transition, characterizing the 1^3B_1 state in the pristine arylnitrene compound (Table 1), is shifted at a higher energy (4.145 eV).

Table 3. Vertical excitation energy (in eV), main configurations and oscillator strength (f_{osc}) of the lowest triplet and singlet states computed at FIC-NEVPT2(10,10)/def2TZVP level of theory for the NH₂-2CN aryl nitrene derivative.

state	ΔE	main configurations	f_{osc}
X ³ A ₂	0.000	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(n_x)^1 $	-
1 ¹ A ₂	0.855	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(n_x)^1 $	-
1 ¹ A ₁	1.073	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^2 $	-
2 ¹ A ₁	2.620	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_x)^2 $	-
1 ³ B ₁	2.741	$ (\sigma)^2(1\pi)^2(2\pi)^2(3\pi)^2(n_y)^1(3\pi^*)^1 $	0.020

This analysis demonstrates how the rational molecular design can efficiently modulate the electronic structure of the aryl nitrene systems, allowing an optimal tuning of their excited state energy, nature and photoluminescence properties.

In this work, we have computationally assessed the potential of aryl nitrenes as optically addressable molecular spin systems. Our high-accuracy calculations confirm a triplet ground state, where the two unpaired electrons are predominantly localized on the nitrogen atom. This electronic structure gives rise to substantial energy gaps between the triplet ground state, the open-shell singlet state of the same symmetry, and the higher-lying closed-shell excited states. The state ordering and molecular symmetry of aryl nitrene create favorable conditions for spin-state initialization. Our SOC calculations confirm that ISC selectively depopulates the $M_S = \pm 1$ sublevels, while spin-vibronically assisted RISC from the lowest singlet state exclusively populates the $M_S = 0$ sublevel of the triplet ground state. This mechanism enables efficient spin polarization, a key requirement for optically addressable spin systems. A potential drawback of pristine aryl nitrene is the weak optical response of its lowest excited triplet state, which could limit photoluminescence and hinder optical readout. However, we demonstrate that rational chemical substitution with electron donor and acceptor groups can overcome this limitation. By altering the electronic nature of the lowest excited state, while preserving its symmetry, these modifications significantly enhance the transition dipole moment between the triplet ground and excited states, making fluorescence-based detection more feasible. These findings are particularly promising given recent experimental advances in the stabilization of aryl nitrene derivatives and the precise spatial control of nitrene centers through the photolysis of azide molecular crystals. This level of control, which remains a challenge for NV⁻ centers, could open new avenues for the development of molecular spin qubits and quantum interfaces. Although this work focuses on spin-state initialization, future studies should explore optical coherence in aryl nitrenes, an essential feature for quantum technologies.

Methods

The molecular geometry has been optimized within the Unrestricted Kohn-Sham (UKS) and the Restricted KS (RKS) formalism for the triplet and singlet ground state, respectively, employing PBE0 functional.⁴⁴ All real frequencies have been obtained. The triplet solution turned out to be the most stable one, lying 2.155 eV below the singlet. The State Averaged Complete Active Space Self Consistent Field (SA-CASSCF) calculations were ran employing natural orbitals computed at Møller-Plesset 2nd order perturbation theory (MP2) level. The N-Electron Valence 2nd order Perturbation Theory (NEVPT2)⁴⁵ were carried out within the Fully Internally Contracted (FIC-NEVPT2)⁴⁶ approximation. For both CASSCF and NEVPT2, an active space of 10 electrons in 10 orbitals (10,10) has been chosen (Figure 3), requesting 8 triplets and 8 singlets in the same calculation. The SA-CASSCF and FIC-NEVPT2 calculations were ran on top of the DFT optimized geometry. The RI-JK approximation with the def2/JK auxiliary basis set has been employed in the SA-CASSCF and FIC-NEVPT2 calculations. The Spin-Orbit Coupling (SOC) matrix elements have been computed at SA-CASSCF(10,10) level of theory. In all the calculations the def2-TZVP basis set has been employed. The DFT calculations were performed using Gaussian 16 software,⁴⁷ while the MP2, SA-CASSCF and FIC-NEVPT2 calculations were ran using ORCA 6.0.⁴⁸

The orbital interaction diagram and the calculation of the exchange integral were done using Multiwfn/3.8.^{49,50}

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information file includes: visualization of the vibrational normal mode used to displace the molecular geometry of arylnitrene; SA-CASSCF natural orbitals of the arylnitrene derivative; discussion of the spin-polarized ISC in molecular basis.

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